

POLLUTION AND ITS EFFECT ON DEWAS ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

From the age old period, man & environment have been an integral part each other. Over the years hence has been a spreading of environmental consciousness. The current focus on environment is not new is it has been a part of Indian culture for a long time. But various change have a shock the balance both human life & environment.

One of the major the environment is water pollution. The main source of water pollution are sewage, increasing pollution density, dumping of agriculture of and industrial waste reduce flow of water in to lakes due to withdrawal for irrigation and cultivation and inversion of idols during festivals. Fresh water lakes, river & ground water get contaminated and in turn, there is storage in the supply of drinking water crop get infected. People contract diseases like, dysentery, indigestion, skin irritation which some times proves fatal.

Keywords:

Dewas Industry, Dewas environment, Industrial pollution in Dewas.

INTRODUCTION

Dewas is highly polluted city in Dewas city are many industrial, hospital and nursing home

1. Large scale industrial 06
2. Medium scale industrial 57
3. Small scale industrial 63
4. Hospital and Nursing Home. 20

INDUSTRIAL SOURCES

Industrial consuming big amount of energy raw material & water.

Table 1:

	PH	CI	T.S.	Cond.
K.W. Kshipra	8.60	2.3/10	64.6677	780
Tata	8.25	15.7/10	68.5475	3520
Ranbaxy	8.00	5.8/10	64.8936	2420
	C1= 2.3 x 500/10			

In the Dewas city all at this waste water from the factories is discharged directly into the city's channel system some channel are heavily polluted from the industrial waste. At some places the PH touches 1-2 an oil film covers the water surface to prevent oxygen transfer the dye cause was colour in the water.

MUNICIPAL SOURCES

The anaerobic condition, offensive smell of the D.O.C. on the station in rainy season is easily sensed which is intolerable.

Level of pollution	No. of industries	Air pollution	% of Air pollution	Water pollution		% & industries which produce waste product		
Industries spread highly pollution	27	2.5	18%	23	16%	14%	21	15%
	36	11%	8%	12	8%	3%	4	3%
	76	01%	72%	-	-	17%		
	139	37%	-	35	24%		25	18%

The table shows that in Dewas 139 industries out of 139, 26 highly spread pollution 11% medium spread pollution and 01 low spread pollution industries are nil. But in real life production carry some pollutant with it. The industries which highly pollution level are responsible for harmful waste product plastic, steel metal soyabin D.O.C. Dye and intermediate formecitble electric bulb are produce by leather factories etc. Approximate 18% industries are include.

STRATEGIES FOR WATER QUALITY MANAGEMENT OF KSHIPRA

Latest process techniques for reducing the waste water generation, efficient use of the raw material for least generation attempting a recovery and by product system modifying the waste generating process. Re-using and recycling of effluents waste load equivalent to reduced peak flow tailoring production in the tube with assimilative capacity of receiving water in extreme and emergent situation etc.)

CONCLUSION

The environmental problem exist in the both cases that is for the existing industries as well as for a cluster of Dewas industries the problem associated with the existing industries are easy to tackle. Environmental aspect of such industries it is felt necessary to plan the strategies for proper management of environment leading to sustainable development.

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